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Abstract No: PO-10

Electrical conductivity measurements of cellulose-based gas diffusion layers with and without microporous layer for proton exchange membrane fuel cells

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The commitment to sustainable and cost-effective energy solutions increased the need for alternative materials for fuel cell components. Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) fuel cells, known to be efficient and green, demand high-performance GDLs that will facilitate easy electron transport, gas permeability, and water management. Conventional GDLs constructed from carbon paper or cloth are efficient but costly, non-renewable, and environmentally unsafe. To solve these issues, this study explores the feasibility of using RISO master paper, a porous cellulose-based paper, as a GDL material by functionalization via a graphite-epoxy composite. The study investigates the influences of layering and microporous coating on the electrical properties that are required for PEMFC functionality. A series of four base layers (Layers 01–04) were fabricated using a combination of Riso master paper (hemp cellulose-based) and conductive fillers by the dip coating method. Then, the MPL layer was air spray-coated onto one side of the samples for enhanced surface conductivity and hydrophobicity. This comprised the application of a carbon black and 2-isopropanol mixture, and it was tested for electrical conductivity. The final values were determined by taking the mean values of the data from three separate locations in each sample to increase precision and repeatability. Electrical Conductivity was calculated from resistance (R), area (A), and thickness (L). Resistance (R) values were taken from Potentiostat Linear Sweep Voltammetry (LSV) analysis data in a Swagelok Cell. The results indicate that electrical conductivity may be significantly enhanced in some materials by the addition of the MPL. Layer 01 with MPL, in particular, had a remarkable conductivity of 0.939 S/m, as opposed to its original value of 0.234 S/m. Yet not all the layers responded in the same way; Layer 04, for instance, showed a decline in conductivity following MPL treatment, from 0.343 to 0.115 S/m. These findings show that conductivity improvements are very much a function of layer composition, MPL thickness, uniformity, and quality of interfacial bonding. Not every combination was enhanced, however, with a keen focus on layer compatibility and deposition control. Additional studies are required to optimize MPL formulation (binder content, carbon black type, and particle size), discuss durability and water management, and develop scalable manufacturing techniques. Overall, the study indicates the creation of low-cost and environmentally friendly GDL alternatives that could result in the wider use of PEM fuel cells within green energy systems and create sustainable and very efficient components for future fuel cell systems.

Keywords: Cellulose, Electrical Conductivity, Gas Diffusion, Microporous, Sustainability

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